

ON-BOARD MULTISPECTRAL IMAGE COMPRESSION WITH AN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

Remote Sensing (RS) is applied for a variety of purposes, thanks to the large availability of heterogeneous data. Furthermore, the growing number of CubeSat missions is encouraging increasingly advanced, flexible, and configurable RS missions, that also include the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on-board. Indeed, specific hardware allows advanced processing on-board the satellites even if the computational capability is not the same as on the ground. In the context of on-board processing, the compression of acquired images is crucial because permits to save bandwidth for data transmission. We propose an AI-based lossy image compression algorithm for multispectral images that can be executed on-board a CubeSat. The algorithm is based on a Convolutional AutoEncoder (CAE) Neural Network (NN). In lossy compression part of the information stored in the original image is lost. Therefore, the results evaluation includes the assessment of the usability of the decompressed images for common applications.

Index Terms— on-board processing, artificial intelligence, image compression, multispectral images, cubesats

1. INTRODUCTION

Remote Sensing (RS) can provide useful information at different spatial and temporal scales. The development of new technologies and the large quantities of data obtained from different RS platforms have made its application possible in all areas of Earth science [1]. Today a growing number of sensors are mounted on micro- or nano-satellites, namely CubeSats, that are revolutionizing the Earth Observation (EO) field. In fact, CubeSats are smaller than traditional satellites, have shorter development time and launch costs, and often have higher spatio-temporal resolutions [2]. For these reasons they are used in industry and research to develop innovative missions. Nevertheless, one of their main limitations is the computational capacity, especially in up- and downlink bandwidth and on-board computing power. However, recent advances in commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) edge processors

allows efficient execution of advanced data processing operations on-board, including those based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms [3].

AI methods, including Deep Learning (DL), represent a well-established technology also in the field of RS. Indeed, DL algorithms can extract relevant information from RS data, generally leading to better results than traditional methods. Nowadays, the ultimate challenge is to effectively use AI onboard, to efficiently increase the imaging product value, deliver meaningful and useful data to end-users, and optimize the use of downlink bandwidth [3], [4]. For example, the European Space Agency (ESA) proved the possibility and benefits of using AI in space with the Φ -Sat-1 and Φ -Sat-2 CubeSat missions. Φ -Sat-1 was successfully launched in September 2020 with an on-board AI-based cloud detection algorithm [5]. Φ -Sat-2 is still under development and aims at running different AI-based applications on a CubeSat platform. In particular, a 6U CubeSat will carry on-board a multispectral optical camera and the Intel Movidius™ Myriad™ 2 AI processor. The latter is a Vision Processing Unit (VPU), i.e., an accelerator developed to efficiently run deep NN algorithms and suited to be used in space. The AI-based applications can be developed, installed, validated, and operated on the spacecraft during flight within the NanoSat MO Framework [6]. Φ -Sat-2 will contain a set of default AI applications, which will cover different DL approaches such as supervised (image segmentation, object detection) and unsupervised learning (with AutoEncoders (AEs) and generative networks) [7].

Within this context, the efficient compression of acquired RS images is a matter of key importance. Image compression is the technique used to minimize the size of an image and two main approaches to image compression exist: lossy and lossless. Unlike lossless compression, in lossy compression the size of the resulting image is significantly reduced but part of the information stored in the original image is lost [8]. In addition to traditional image compression algorithms, DL algorithms have also been successfully applied in this field. The most used deep NN types for image compression are AEs, i.e., NNs with an encoding–decoding structure for image compression and

reconstruction, Variational AutoEncoders, Generative Adversarial Networks, and Recurrent Neural Networks [9].

Fig. 1. CAE structure. The original input image is fed into the encoder part to extract the compressed representation through the bottleneck layer. The image is reconstructed in the decoder part. Conv stands for convolutional.

We present here an algorithm for lossy compression of MultiSpectral (MS) images based on a Convolutional Autoencoder (CAE), i.e., an AE with convolutional layers. This specific architecture enables us to achieve the benefits of a lossy compression algorithm in terms of compression ratio while still retaining the ability to reconstruct the original image, a capability generally absent in traditional lossy compression algorithms. Furthermore, this AI-based approach allows us to minimize information loss by leveraging the CNN's ability to capture nonlinear relationships between neighboring pixels both spectrally and spatially. The algorithm can run on-board the CubeSat developed within the Φ -Sat-2 mission and was tested on the Myriad VPU. The encoder part of the CAE compresses onboard the acquired images while the decoder is used at the ground segment, to reconstruct the original acquisitions. The quality of the reconstructed images is evaluated by means of standard image similarity metrics, that are Peak Signal-toNoise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) [10], but also with applicative metrics that aims at assessing the practical use of the reconstructed images. The decompressed images were indeed tested in real application scenario, that include Normalized Different Vegetation Index (NDVI) calculation and semantic segmentation for the detection of urban areas. The results obtained with this algorithm should currently be considered as a standalone benchmark.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Dataset

The dataset used for training and validating the algorithm consists of 9 Sentinel-2 acquisitions at L1C processing level that depicts different scenes, including urban areas, coastal areas, forests, glaciers, mountains, deserts. Sentinel-2 images were converted to simulate the Φ -Sat-2 acquisitions through a processing chain that includes the selection of the matching spectral bands and the simulation of the spatial resolution,

Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), and Modulation Transfer Function (MTF) of the Φ -Sat-2 camera. The latter is a multispectral push-broom imager, has 7-band in the visible and near-infrared spectral range, and a 4.75 m GSD [7].

Pre-processing steps also include normalization and tiling. Final dataset consists of 57,600 patches shaped $256 \times 256 \times 7$. Thus, the input of the network is an image with dimension $256 \times 256 \times 7$, where 7 is the number of the original acquisition bands. Finally, the dataset was split into training, validation, and test sets with a proportion of 0.80, 0.10, 0.10.

2.2. CAE Model

The model architecture is based on AEs, a NN topology consisting of an encoding part and a decoding part and an internal bottleneck layer that forces a compressed representation of the original input [11]. A schematic representation of the model is shown in Fig. 1. After the training phase, the encoder and decoder parts are used separately, i.e., the encoder on-board and the decoder on the ground. The final definition of the model was determined firstly taking into account the requirements imposed by the mission, especially in terms of memory footprint and RAM usage. Secondly, the number of layers and their parameters were defined with a trial-and-error approach, also considering the compromise between reaching a significant compression and limiting information loss. At the end, the input layer has a size of $256 \times 256 \times 7$, while the bottleneck layer is $32 \times 32 \times 5$. This means that the Compression Ratio (CR), i.e., the ratio between the input image size and the compressed image size, is of 89.6.

2.3. Evaluation metrics

PSNR and SSIM are commonly used to evaluate the similarity between two images. PSNR depends on Mean Squared Error (MSE) and higher PSNR values indicate higher image quality. SSIM is related to the perception of image quality by the human eye and depends on mean luminance, standard deviation, and covariance between the two images, and ranges between 0 and 1 [10]. The algorithm performance was also evaluated in terms of application of the reconstructed images to common application cases that include generation of NDVI maps and the detection of urban areas with a semantic segmentation algorithm based on a UNet NN. The main purpose of this evaluation strategy is to try to provide information about the quality of information lost during the compression process.

3. RESULTS 3.1. Model training

The model was trained in Python 3.10.12 with TensorFlow 2.13.0. Training process took 304 epochs, using the early stopping callback; L1 and L2 regularization methods were

used to prevent overfitting. A custom learning rate scheduler was implemented to prevent loss function from oscillating

Fig. 2. Encoder output. The output of the encoder part of the CAE can be represented as a multichannel image with 5 bands.

Fig. 3. Decoder output for a single band image. (a) Original acquisition in band 3. (b) Reconstructed image in band 3. (c) Values distribution for the original image. (d) Values distribution for the reconstructed image.

indefinitely once close to the solution. It was used Adam optimizer, and a custom loss function that combines the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) with the SSIM. The addition of SSIM indeed has proved to be beneficial for the results of the training process. The balance between the two terms was controlled with two parameters that for the best configuration were found to be 0.4 and 0.6, respectively.

3.2. Encoder and decoder output

The output of the encoder part is a compressed version of the original input, that has a size of $32 \times 32 \times 5$, compared to the original $256 \times 256 \times 7$. It can be represented as a multichannel image with 5 different bands representing the latent feature space, as shown in Fig. 2. Each image in the figure has a size of 512×512 , obtained by mosaicking each 32×32 patch to reconstruct the original input acquisition.

The output of the decoder is the image reconstructed after the compression and has a size of $256 \times 256 \times 7$. Each

Table I. Model performances on Test Set.

	Average Value	Standard Deviation	Confidence Interval (95%)
PSNR	50.458	2.095	(50.220, 50.696)
SSIM	0.9991	$6.960 \cdot 10^{-4}$	(0.9989, 0.9991)

Fig. 4. NDVI map obtained from (a) the original image and from (b) the reconstructed image. Values distribution for the NDVI map obtained from (c) the original image and from (d) the reconstructed image.

patch is combined to return the original input image size. The output of the decoder is shown in Fig. 3 (b), while Fig. 3 (a) shown the original acquisition in band 3. Fig. 3 (c) and (d) illustrate the histogram for the original and reconstructed image. As shown in the picture, values distribution is preserved after the processes of compression and reconstruction.

3.3. Results evaluation

As defined in Section 2.3, results were evaluated in terms of PSNR and SSIM and in the applicative cases of NDVI mapping and detection of the urban areas. Table I reports the results obtained for the test set in terms of PSNR and SSIM calculated as the average value, together with other statistics as standard deviation and confidence interval at 95%.

Concerning the applicative metrics, the results obtained for NDVI maps are shown in Fig. 4 that represents the maps obtained taking as input the original and the decompressed image, and their corresponding histogram distribution. The detection of urban areas instead is performed as a semantic

segmentation task with a UNet model. The trained model is used to predict urban areas masks taking as input both the original and the decompressed image, as shown in in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Probability map of urban areas obtained from (a) the original image and from (b) the reconstructed image. Binary map of urban areas (in white) obtained from (c) the original image and from (d) the reconstructed image.

Fig. 5 (a) and (b) show the probability of detecting urban areas in the original and decompressed images, respectively, while (c) and (d) the binary maps obtained after setting a threshold value. The number of pixels classified as urban area, i.e., the white pixels, are shown as a percentage in Fig. 5 (c) and (d). These values are slightly different, proving that a few differences exist between the two maps. The compression algorithm's inference was initially performed on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 Ti GPU, taking an average of 8.67 seconds to compress the 7 original bands of an entire Φ -Sat-2 image, comprised of 256 patches (256, 256, 7). Subsequently, the model underwent inference testing on the Myriad 2 VPU, the onboard inference hardware for the CubeSat, after being tailored for compatibility. This process took 215.64 seconds for the same task, translating to 26.29 seconds per band. Notably, performance met ESA's acceptance criteria for execution time, model size (53.248KB for this encoder), and SSIM and PSNR scores.

4. CONCLUSION

The CAE based algorithm proposed in this study can compress multispectral images with a CR equal to 89.6 with a limited information loss, as proved by the results evaluated in terms of PSNR, SSIM and applicability of the decompressed images. Indeed, they were tested for the cases related to NDVI maps generation and semantic segmentation for detecting urban areas. In particular, the maps obtained

with the decompressed images are comparable to those obtained with the original. This is true for both NDVI maps, as shown by comparing the histograms of the two images, and the detection of urban areas for which the percentage of "urban" pixels has been evaluated. Due to its characteristics related to memory consumption and size, this AI-based algorithm can be implemented on-board a CubeSat, allowing to save bandwidth for data transmission and storage space. These themes are of increasing importance in this EO era, characterized by the use of AI also in space and the huge amount of available data.

It is important to note that training the model on simulated data may initially lead to discrepancies when applied to real on-board data. However, multiple fine-tuning steps have been planned for the model once real Φ -Sat-2 images are obtained. This iterative process will help adjust the model parameters to better align with actual data, thereby enhancing accuracy and performance over time. Furthermore, the ability to update the model during the mission is a critical aspect of our approach. As the mission progresses and more real data is collected, model will be refined to ensure it remains accurate and effective.

Beyond the mentioned fine-tuning, we plan to upgrade the model by reducing the number of target bands in the CAE's bottleneck layer, thus increasing the compression factor. Additionally, we aim to conduct a thorough comparison of our model with other existing algorithms for compressing and reconstructing multispectral satellite images.

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